

USEFUL PROPERTIES OF LENTILS

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Abstract: *Lentils have become an important factor in providing a nutritious diet in the countries of the world. In terms of economic efficiency obtained by growing lentils, it ranks higher than other grain crops. Like many other legumes, it has an easily digestible protein content. The amount of protein in the seeds of lentil varieties is 26-31%. This article presents the importance and useful aspects of lentil, one of the leguminous crops, for the human body and gives conclusions.*

Key words: *Legumes, lentils, food, food unit, protein, immunity, antioxidant.*

Lentil is an annual plant belonging to the legume family. Lentils have been used since ancient times in Central Asia and many European countries. Nowadays, Turkish dishes made from lentils are a tradition in national cuisines. Lentils are rich in useful microelements such as calcium, magnesium, potassium, phosphorus and iron. There are fatty acids such as omega 3 and omega 6 that are beneficial for skin and hair. Compared to other legumes, lentils contain more folic acid. Lentil is a plant rich in proteins, lentil grain contains 23-32% protein. It is very useful for the human body. Soluble fiber in lentils improves digestion and boosts immunity. Lentil plant is a dietary plant. It consists of 54% complex carbohydrates and 26% proteins that are quickly digested in the body. In addition, lentils contain very little fat. That's why this grain product is an excellent product for those who pay attention to their figure. Foods made from such grain products are digestible for a long time and make you feel full for a long time. Lentils are very useful. It reduces the amount of sugar in the blood, it is in the first place in the storage of iron with many connective tissues. Green lentils are the most useful.

Because green lentils are a grain that has a lot of connective tissue. In addition, the lentil plant is rich in vitamins A and C, rich in group B drugs. According to its nutritional value, lentils can replace bread and, in a certain sense, meat. Due to the Mg element in the lentil plant, it can be a cure for nervous and heart diseases. Also, lentil plant contains tryptophan, and after entering the human body, maskur amino acid turns into serotonin hormone, which is called the hormone of happiness. Qualified doctors are recommending the lentil plant and the dishes prepared from it to the patients. Chinese doctors said that lentil plant is one of the products that heat up the client. Therefore, dishes prepared from it are considered healing in cold days. There are several other features of the lentil plant. Since lentils contain antioxidants, they slow down oxidative stress in the body, calm the nerves, and reduce the risk of inflammation and chronic diseases. Antioxidants also prevent rapid aging of a person. Therefore, lentils are an excellent helper in maintaining the youth of not only the skin, but also the whole body. There are different varieties of lentils that differ in taste and color. In terms of nutrients, all types of lentils are about the same, but green lentils have more protein and calcium. They are better than red lentils. It keeps a shell containing many clechatka. Red lentils set a record for the amount of iron and calcium in the world. These substances control the correct metabolism, as well as the amount of hemoglobin. Black lentils can provide the bulk of vitamin E and zinc. The combination of these two substances has a beneficial effect on the functioning of the endocrine, reproductive and nervous systems. Experts recommend eating lentils to lower blood sugar levels for people with diabetes. Dishes made from lentils are also recommended for the treatment of meda and duodenal ulcer, constipation.

In conclusion, the lentil plant, which is a legume, is important in solving the problem of protein necessary for the human body and in the treatment of various diseases.

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